

THE ROLE OF BUSINESS ENGLISH IN MODERN LOGISTICS

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Abstract: The article considers the issue of the English language as a universal means of communication for specialists. The author provides data on the leading position of the English language and its role for business. To update the value of English for logistics, the article reveals answers to the following questions: what is the approximate number of basic scientific terms in logistics, how they are distributed in the areas of logistics, what terms are most used, what sciences logistics is associated with, how many terms logistics uses from related sciences. The study was carried out using the linguo-statistical method of the English dictionary of logistics and authentic texts. The author concludes that English proficiency in logistics is the key to successful business.

Keywords: logistical channel - logistical pipeline - distribution channel - marketing channel business logistics - materials management - physical distribution, logistics activities, negotiations, business, professional vocabulary, international activities, communication, global language, terminology

Introduction

Business English is essential for those who want to become an employee of an international logistics company or do serious business in this area with partners from other countries. Competent command of written and spoken English is a serious sign of business culture, level of education and general status of a specialist. Fluency in special and business terminology in English when negotiating, signing contracts, and business communication is the main fundamental work of logisticians.

English is very important for most professions; it is not for nothing that they begin to learn it from school. One of these professions is logistics. In addition, about the weakening of the humanitarian component general professional training of students is out of the question. [1, 15-20] The formation of the professional competence of a

logistician at the present stage of development of higher education is unthinkable without integration into the general system of language training. Against the backdrop of rapidly developing industrial and scientific relations with foreign countries, one of the requirements for university graduates is the practical knowledge of foreign languages. It is important to prepare students to overcome the language barrier in countries where this language is official. Future professionals need to be introduced to the features of the chosen profession and the role of a foreign language in modern science. When teaching foreign languages at a technical university, it is necessary to pay attention to the volume of language and speech material, to the determination of priorities in the choice of future activities and the corresponding speech skills. It is important to be able to analyze the training of undergraduates and graduate students, identify the main difficulties in translating authentic texts, and determine the factors that influenced the choice of this problem. It is important that the content of the subject contains mechanisms that reveal the possibility of the practical use of a foreign language as an important means of developing and satisfying the interests of students, including non-linguistic ones. The openness of modern society, the renewal of higher professional education, the growing need for specialists who speak foreign languages, require significant changes in the content, structure, organization and technology of teaching foreign languages. The ability to speak a foreign language today is one of the conditions for the professional competence of future logisticians. Many logistics companies cooperate with foreign firms, and ignorance of English on our part will look tactless. And, of course, it will be possible to save on the salary of translators if you yourself know the language.

English technical, colloquial, business, advanced, or at least upper-intermediate - you will not surprise anyone with such requests in the job description. Companies increasingly impose language requirements even when the position itself does not imply English-speaking contacts or the use of foreign sources. It will soon be the case that asking a job candidate if he speaks English will be as indecent as asking if he knows how to use a computer. [1, 30-45] There is nowhere without a foreign language now - this is a common point of view of recruitment managers of large companies and recruitment agencies. The larger the company and the higher the position, the more often "mandatory knowledge of a foreign language", usually English, is found in the requirements for an employee. In addition, although the cost of a specialist in the labor market does not increase, but knowledge of English increases the chances of a candidate for employment, since it allows him to consider a wider range of vacancies. "The fact that most of today's job descriptions include upper-intermediate English as a mandatory requirement is indisputable. Knowledge of a foreign language today is, if not a pass to the company, then at least admission to participate in the "competitive selection". Among other things, knowledge of English also allows a specialist to maintain their competitiveness. Other things being

equal, employers always prefer to hire someone with great skills, even if not all of them will be in demand in the current position. There is no single explanation for this phenomenon, but with a high degree of probability, we can say that some kind of psychological factor is triggered. [2, 60-65] Thus, it is necessary to introduce a conceptual and technological model of teaching foreign languages into the educational process, which is determined by the communicative and cognitive needs of specialists in the relevant field. The goal of this introduction will forever remain the knowledge of a foreign language both in production and scientific activities, and for self-education. Logistics specialists are often faced with the need to confidently communicate in English on the phone, conduct business and correspond with foreign partners, read information materials, understand the intricacies of contracts in English, and master the special vocabulary used in the field of logistics operations and transportation of goods. Any work is often associated with the search and receipt of information and the work of a logistics specialist is directly related to this, where knowledge of English is necessary. The opportunity to get interesting, reliable, specific and required information increases by tens and hundreds of times - if you work in the English-speaking information space - as millions of web pages are in English!

Methods and results

Ludwig Wittgenstein: "The limits of my language mean the limits of my world." As Wittgenstein argues the use of language to express thought is a means to map the boundaries of reality.

According to the academic association Global Language Monitor [2, 150], English is the official language in 53 countries and is spoken by about 2 billion people. For 400 million people, English is the main language. About 95% of all e-mail is in English, and about 28% of all books in the world are published in it. About 85% of international organizations and conferences around the world use it as a working one.

According to a study in the field of cross-cultural management by experts from the Harvard Business Review [2, 150-155], business experience confirms that it is much more convenient to conduct international business in one common language, so English is gradually becoming the official language in global companies, even if their head offices are not in English speaking countries. Successful business activities often involve communicating with customers, suppliers and partners, not all of whom share a common mother tongue. Companies that do not speak English severely limit their growth opportunities and may lose out to their competitors who have adopted it. Moreover, English helps to unite employees of companies from different countries in solving common problems, because in business correspondence, negotiations, and conclusion of large transactions, companies prefer English as a working language. Moreover, in cases where cross-cultural integration of foreign employees slows down or complicates cooperation, English acts as a mediating language and culture.

Logistics, in turn, is a clear example of the effective use of English for communication of multilingual partners. For example, after World War II, the United States provided significant support to the development of the Japanese economy, which later became the ideologist of such world-famous logistics management concepts in the field of production and services as “Just-in-time” and total quality logistics systems. [2, 155] Logistics specialists are often faced with the need to confidently communicate in English on the phone, conduct business and correspond with foreign partners, read information materials, understand the intricacies of contracts in English, and master the special vocabulary used in the field of logistics operations and transportation of goods. Any work is often associated with the search and receipt of information and the work of a logistics specialist is directly related to this, where knowledge of English is necessary. The opportunity to get interesting, reliable, specific and required information increases by tens and hundreds of times - if you work in the English-speaking information space - as millions of web pages are in English!

Since there are only a few terms in Japanese in logistics (chaku-chaku, kaizen, Kanban, poka-yoke), and the rest are only in English, it is clear that the communication took place in an international language. In the scientific and practical life of logistics, English prevails as the language of international communication, which is evident from the number of electronic English-language dictionaries and glossaries of logistics terms, as well as books, articles and studies in this area [2, 200].

Let's consider the state of the global language of logistics in order to update it for professional activities. The objectives of this study include the following questions:

- *What is the approximate number of basic scientific concepts in logistics?*
- *How are they distributed among logistics areas?*
- *What are the most commonly used terms?*
- *What are the sciences related to logistics?*
- *Approximately how many terms does logistics use from related sciences?*

The corpus of authentic texts on logistics and management from the electronic database **ProQuest** in the amount of about 14,500 words, as well as the corpus of English terms from the terminological dictionary Terminology of Logistics of the European Logistics Association (ELA) [3, 100-102] was used as the material of the study. Using the methods of descriptive and comparative analysis, the lexicographic method, the method of contextual semantic analysis, the linguo-statistical method, as well as the inductive-deductive method, the question of the peculiarities of the English language for logistics was considered. Consider some characteristics of the English language of logistics:

- *the number of terms in the areas of logistics*
- *commonly used logistics terms*

- *the number of terms borrowed from related fields of knowledge*
- *homonymy*
- *polysemy*
- *synonymy*

Analyzing the ways of forming the terminology of a certain field of knowledge, one can see that they coincide with the ways of creating sets of lexical units inherent in this natural language as a whole [3, 105]. Therefore, the distribution of English terms of logistics in its directions was carried out in accordance with the theory of lexicology, when each special thematic area was filled only with terms that were really specific to this topic [3,105-106]. The classification of terms was based on their definitions, recorded in the dictionary Terminology of Logistics (1397 entries). Using the works of V.I. Sergeev [3, 108-110], we identified nine sections of logistics, in which the English terms were distributed as follows.

1. *logistics support for production 18%*
2. *transportation 17%^{iv}*
3. *Purchasing management 17%^v*
4. *stock management 11%*
5. *management of logistics systems 11%*
6. *warehousing and cargo handling 9%*
7. *order management 8%^{vi}*
8. *supply chain management 6%*
9. *information support of logistics 3% (frequently used logistics terms.)*

When studying English in logistics, the terms that were often used to form new terms were also considered. From the Terminology of Logistics dictionary, 46 main terms (3% of the dictionary) were identified, which are part of 77% of all head terms in the dictionary. Thus, the most commonly used terms in logistics are as follows: [3, 220-225]

1. *product (product) - 7% of the terms formed with it,*
2. *order -6.5%,*
3. *cargo - 5.7%,*
4. *stock - 5.3%*
5. *planning - 4.3%,*
6. *transport - 3.4%,*
7. *material - 3.1%*
8. *shipping (transportation) - 2.7%,*
9. *system - 2.7%*
10. *load - 2.3%*

The language of logistics can be considered complexly, since it is formed on the interaction of several initial terminological systems of sciences related to logistics. In the ELA Terminology of Logistics dictionary, marks were used when the term itself or one of its meanings is used in other areas of knowledge, and the definitions themselves, which meant that the term is universal for several areas of knowledge. Thus, the analysis showed that only 3% of the terms are absolutely new

and are not found anywhere else, except for logistics [3, 230]. 97% were distributed as follows:

- *management* 42%
- *transport* 14%
- *commercial activities* 13%
- *technology* 11%
- *mechanical engineering* 4.5%
- *marketing* 3.5%
- *international economic relations* 3%
- *law* 2%
- *mathematics* 2%
- *informatics* 1.9%
- *accounting* 0.1%

Speaking about the language of science, one should pay attention to the content of the concept of "term". In general, the theory of any science is expressed by a certain system of concepts, which, when expressed in words, become terms. The whole theory of science is created using terms that regulate and streamline its special concepts and knowledge. Thus, a set of terms - in other words, terminology - is a kind of "language" of any science, industry, activity or knowledge. With the help of terms, scientific and practically significant information is distributed between people, and through the translation of specialized literature and documentation - between different countries [3, 235]. An ideal term has several interpretations from the standpoint of logic, semiotics, epistemology. Almost all researchers agree that terms from the standpoint of logic should be context-^{vii}^{viii}independent, unambiguous, meaningfully accurate and systemic. But, in English-language logistics, the situation with non-ideal terms is as follows: [3, 240-245]

Homonymy. One of the conditions for an ordered terminology is the absence of homonymy, which is carried out in logistics in English - 0.3% of 1397 terms.

Polysemy. Polysemantic terms make up 7% of the English terminology of logistics and have from 2 to 5 meanings. The words market (mart, sales region) and receipt (acceptance, receipt, invoice, claim check, arrival, cash receipt) have the most meanings.

Synonymy. In the English terminology of logistics there are:

- parallel terms borrowed into English and their English counterparts, for example, French. voyage - eng. trip (flight); French barge lighter (barge); French vendor - English supplier (supplier); French consignment - eng. shipment(sending); English loss – French damage (damage).
- Equivalent full and short terms: ABC period planning– ABC planning (ABC planning); forklift pockets – fork pockets (recess in a container for a forklift fork); harmonized commodity description and coding system – harmonized system

(harmonized system); product load profile – load profile (product profile); business logistics - logistics (logistics); product configuration - configuration; roll on / roll off - ro-ro (ro-ro transportation); full truck load - truckload (machine shipment), gross profit margin – gross margin (profit margin); freight bill-of-lading – freight bill (consignment note).

- terms that differ only in word order: capacity buying - buying capacity; depth of penetration of the customer order - penetration depth of the customer; depth of penetration of the design - penetration depth of the design; service level - level of service; terms of delivery - delivery terms.

Logistics – Business Logistics - Materials Management - Physical Distribution

In foreign logistics practice and university courses, the concepts of materials management, logistics and physical distribution are often used on an equal footing. Materials management and logistics are sometimes understood in the same way and are interchanged when it comes to the functions and areas of material management of an industrial enterprise [4, 185-190]. It can be concluded that both concepts mean the movement of materials and products (or the flow of goods) throughout the entire production process. The concept of logistics is still broader, as it includes more functions. Next, we should compare the concepts of physical distribution and logistics. The fact is that in the period from the 1950s to the mid-1970s, the concept of physical distribution meant what is now included in the concept of logistics. In the field of distribution of an industrial or trading company, these concepts are identical [4, 190]. The concepts of materials management and physical distribution are also synonymous, as they mean the movement of goods along the chain from production to distribution. Supply chain: Logistical Chain - Supply Chain Many experts initially used the term supply chain as a synonym for the term logistics [4, 200], which can be judged by the definition of the Council of Logistics Management, but later supply chain management began to be understood more broadly as a new business concept [5, 639]. In 2004, the American organization Council of Supply Chain Management Professionals formulated the definition of supply chain management, which states that supply chain management has a different subject than logistics. The ^{ixx}concepts of supply chain management and logistics in the West are now understood as separate, but closely related areas of activity [5, 650].

Logistical Channel - Logistical Pipeline - Distribution Channel - Marketing Channel

In Western practice, the terms logistical channel and logistical pipeline are often used. Both concepts have a similar meaning: this is the most efficient structure of the commodity flow, where the transportation of goods from the supplier to the buyer is considered as a whole and includes storage, processing, transportation, etc. The term distribution channel (same as marketing channel) sometimes replaces logistical pipeline and logistics channel. Analyzing the content of the concepts of logistical pipeline and distribution channel, we can conclude that the fundamental differences lie in the function of logistics and marketing in channels. [6, 19-22] If,

the distribution channel is formed by firms who are transaction specialists (manufacturer's agents, distributors, commission agents, wholesalers and retailers) and their main purpose is to negotiate, contract and manage sales transactions, then the logistical pipeline is a network of working relationships aimed at ensuring profitable movement and positioning of stocks. [7, 500-502]

Conclusion

We live in a period of rapidly developing international relations, determined largely by the globalization of the economy. The logistics departments of almost all companies are among the first to feel the ongoing changes in the economy and business. Often, components for a particular manufacturing facility located in a provincial town in one country come from different countries and may be shipped to another continent for sale. Transport logisticians are engaged in subtleties of this process.

Professionals in the field of logistics need to be able to:

- *read information materials;*
- *talk in English on the phone;*
- *conduct business correspondence with foreign partners, which requires knowledge of the rules for writing a letter of request, a letter of inquiry, a letter of complaint, etc.;*
- *understand contracts in a foreign language;*
- *deal with complaints in English.*

Some companies put forward additional requirements for transport logisticians:

- *be a confident PC user;*
- *know the rules of international transportation Incoterms;*
- *have certificates of additional education in the field of English.*

Thus, future logisticians should be prepared to carry out specific professional duties in English as the language of international communication.

English logistics language is in demand both in companies operating in the domestic market and in organizations that have entered foreign markets. As the world economy becomes more and more large-scale, knowledge of the English language by logistics specialists is becoming the main attribute of a successful company and^{xi} its leaders. Logistics terms in English are used in almost all business areas of computing, aviation, rail and sea transportation, etc.

“At the moment, English in transport logistics covers almost all areas, from courier delivery around the city to multimodal transportation. The range of different areas, which includes business English for logisticians, is quite wide” [8, 339-342].

Separately, it is worth dwelling on such a topic as a novice logistician with knowledge of English. The fact is that novice specialists who do not have the necessary actual skills, but who speak business English, receive a certain advantage in recruitment over other candidates. In addition, in most cases, a logistician's resume in English has a priority, rather than others. At the same time, one should not

forget that proper business English for logistics is focused on delegating work processes, while the main goal of general English is to improve 4 language skills: *reading, speaking, listening and writing*. With the release of the economy to the international level, the role of the English language has increased significantly. Without understanding the English language, or at least its basics, it is difficult for a logistician to find a job with a decent salary and social package.

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